

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

COLLEGE OF ALLIED HEALTH SCIENCES

PROCEEDINGS OF THE MEETING OF BOARD OF STUDIES HELD ON 11.10.2019 AT 9:30 AM IN THE BOARD ROOM

Members present:

1. Dr. Sham Kishore	Chairman
2. Mr. Naveen Bappanadu	Member
3. Dr. Sukesh	Member
4. Dr. Pavanchand Attavar	Member
5. Dr. Vishrutha K V	Member
6. Ms. Shristina Subba	Member
7. Ms. Sathyajith Karanth	Member
8. Ms. Swathi Krishnan	Member
9. Ms. Laveena D'Souza	Member
10. Ms. Swathi D	Member
11. Mrs. Shwetha B	Member
12. Dr. Vrinda	Member

Leave of Absence:

Leave of Absence was granted to the following members by the Chairman of Board of Studies:

1. Dr. Vrinda (Member)

The BOS discussed the following agenda:

1. Approve the minutes of the last Meeting of the BOS held on 05.03.2019.
2. Approve the Finalized Updates and Changes Proposed for Academic Session 2018-19.
3. Commencement of M.Sc. Courses in Allied Health Sciences.
4. Revise Few Topics in the Course of 'Cardiac Care Technology' and 'Forensic Science'.

The Chairman Dr. Sham Kishore introduced himself, thanking and welcoming all the members who were present for the meeting. The meeting there after deliberated on agenda as had been approved by the Chairperson.

Agenda No. 1: Confirmations of the minutes of Last Meeting of Board of Studies which was held on 05.03.2019. As per the suggestions of the BOS Members in the last meeting, all the Allied Health Sciences Courses were asked to update the changes proposed by the BOS Members.

Agenda No. 2: The Finalized Updates and changes were proposed by the BOS for the Academic Session 2019-18 (Reference Page 3, Table 1) and had to be approved. Resolution was taken accordingly; Updates and Changes were approved as proposed by the BOS.

Agenda No. 3: Discussion regarding the addition of the M.Sc. Courses in Allied Health Sciences, in the Academic Year 2020-21. The BOS approved that the M.Sc. Courses were to be added in the Academic Year 2020-21.

Agenda No. 4: To Revise the Topics of the course of 'Cardiac Care Technology' and Forensic Science' was suggested by Dr. Sham Kishore and Sr. Faculty Ms. Swathi D. The Revised Topics were confirmed and was approved by the BOS as suggested.

The meeting was concluded at 11:30 AM with a vote of thanks by Ms. Swathi D, Member and Board of Studies.

A small, square image showing a handwritten signature in blue ink on a light-colored background. The signature appears to be 'Sham Kishore'.

Dr. Sham Kishore,
Chairman,
BOS in Allied Health Science

Table 1

Addition and Deletion in main subjects, subsidiary, topics in All Allied Health Courses

Course	Topics added/ deleted on BoS proposal	Reason
CCT	Addition: 5th semester: One subject name changed to approach to clinical cardiology	Subjects and topics are similar as Cardiovascular technology, but needs more clinical cardiology experience
B.Sc. FSC	<p>2nd semester- subject: Forensic science 1. Chapter3- identifying psychological disorder-anxiety disorders (panic, phobia, OCD, PTSD signs, symptoms and management)</p> <p>Replaced with- identifying psychotic disorders- introduction and common characteristics, Schizophrenia, undifferentiated types, paranoid types, residual types, catatonic types, diagnostic types, affective disorders, historical background, bipolar disorder, major depressive disorder, characteristics & role of law enforcement officers</p> <p>2. Chapter4: Stress- Hans Model of stress, Lazarus and Folkmann model of stress, sources of stress, stress disease and health, changing health impairing behavior.</p> <p>Replaced with: lie and lie detection- meaning and definition, concept of polygraph, brain mapping, narco analysis and its advantage and disadvantage</p> <p>3. Chapter5: Learning- meaning, definition, theories of learning, Pavlov's classical conditioning, skinner's operant conditioning</p> <p>Replaced with: normal personality in operation- conflicts on defense- introduction, frustration and conflict, guilt and anxiety, defense mechanism- fight and flight, internal defense mechanism, displacement, rationalization, compensation, denial,</p>	Need for modification- the syllabus framed previously focused majorly on general psychology. There was need to modify to forensic importance of psychology.

	<p>repression, identification, fantasy, Sublimation, and isolation</p> <p>4. Chapter 7: psychotherapy- meaning and definition relaxation types</p> <p>Replaced with- psychic criminology- psychics and criminals, types, police view, case history</p> <p>Need for modification- the syllabus framed previously focused majorly on general psychology. There was need to modify to forensic importance of psychology.</p>	
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Table 2
Courses Approved for the academic year 2020-2021

Sl. No	Name of the Coursework
1	B.Sc. - Clinical Psychology
2	M.Sc. - Clinical Psychology
3	M.Sc. Forensic Science
4	M.Sc. Cyber security
5	M.S. Forensic science and criminology
6	M.Sc. Pathology

Members present:

Dr. Sham Kishore

Mr. Naveen Bappanadu

Dr. Sukesh

Dr. Pavanchand Attavar

Dr. Vishrutha K V

Ms. Shristina Subba

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